

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN BASE NORM SPACES AND STRONGLY FACIALLY SYMMETRIC SPACES

¹Ibragimov Mukhtar Mamutovich, ²Arziev Allabay Dzhalgasovich

¹Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh, ²V.I.Romanovsky Institute of Mathematics.
Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13896828>

Abstract. This paper considers the connection between base norm spaces and strongly facially symmetric spaces (SFS-spaces). We investigate the geometric properties of the unit ball in an SFS-space and show that they can be described as base-norm spaces generated by a cone, whose base is a symmetric face possessing a Jordan decomposition. Additionally, we study unitarily geometric tripotents in real SFS-spaces, where under certain conditions these spaces become base norm spaces. The results obtained contribute to a better understanding of SFS-spaces and their role in the axiomatic study of quantum mechanics.

Key words: SFS-space, geometric tripotent, Jordan decomposition, base norm space, radially compact convex set.

Аннотация. В данной работе рассматривается связь между пространствами с базовой нормой и сильно гранево симметричными пространствами (SFS-пространствами). Мы исследуем геометрические свойства единичного шара SFS-пространства и показываем, что их можно описать как пространства с базовой нормой, порожденный конусом, основания которого является симметричная грань, обладающая Йордановым разложением. Также изучаются унитарные геометрические трипотенты в вещественных SFS-пространствах, где при определенных условиях эти пространства становятся пространствами с базовой нормой. Полученные результаты способствуют лучшему пониманию SFS-пространств и их роли в аксиоматическом исследовании квантовой механики.

Ключевые слова: SFS-пространство, геометрический трипотент, Йорданово разложение, пространство с базовой нормой.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada bazaviy normalni fazolar va kuchli qirrali simmetrik fazolar (SFS-fazolar) o'rtasidagi bog'lanish ko'rib chiqiladi. Biz SFS-fazoning birlik sharining geometrik xususiyatlarini o'rganamiz va ularni asosi Jordan yoyilmasiga ega qirra bo'lgan konus tomonidan hosil qilingan bazaviy normalni fazolar sifatida tavsiflash mumkinligini ko'rsatamiz. Shuningdek, haqiqiy SFS-fazolaridagi unitar geometrik tripotentlar o'rganiladi va ma'lum shartlarda ular radial kompaktli qavariq to'plamga ega bazaviy normalni fazo bo'lishi ko'rsatiladi. Olingan natijalar SFS-fazolarini va ularning kvant mexanikasini aksiomatik o'rganishdagi o'rnini yaxshiroq tushunishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: SFS-fazo, geometrik tripotent, Jordan yoyilmasi, bazaviy normalni, radial kompaktli qavariq to'plam

1. Introduction

In the operator algebraic approach to quantum mechanics, algebraic structures are defined in Banach spaces based on a set of geometric axioms that describe quantum measurement processes. Algebraic models for ordered Banach spaces were studied in the works of E. Alfsen and F. Schultz ([2-3]), while Sh. Ayupov and N. Yadgarov investigated convex models in [17]. Y. Friedman and B. Russo, in their studies on facially symmetric spaces [9-13], aimed to identify these algebraic structures in non-ordered Banach spaces where quantum mechanical axioms hold.

They made progress in [9] when the facially symmetric space is reflexive, but further research is needed for the general case. Notably, some results in these spaces were obtained using geometric methods without explicitly defining algebraic structures. This approach was later applied to the study of JB^* and JBW^* -triples. In particular, in [11, Theorems 2.11 and 3.1], it was shown that the predual spaces of von Neumann algebras and JBW^* -triples are neutral SFS-spaces. More general examples of facially symmetric spaces include Banach spaces whose duals are JB^* -triples, such as the dual spaces of C^* -algebras, JB^* -algebras, and J^* -algebras. These structures encompass Hilbert spaces and, in special cases, Cartan factors (see [7-8, 10-11, 16] for more details).

In this paper, we consider the certain geometric properties of the unit ball in facially symmetric spaces, with the aim of gaining deeper insights into the structure of both the spaces themselves and their duals.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. *Let X be a real vector space. A subset V of a space X is called a cone if the following two conditions are satisfied:*

- (i) *if $x \in V$ and $\lambda \geq 0$, then $\lambda x \in V$;*
- (ii) *if $x, y \in V$, then $x + y \in V$.*

For any proper cone $V \subset X$, there exists a corresponding order in X such that

$$x \geq y \Leftrightarrow x - y \in V.$$

A subset K of a cone $V \subset X$ is called the base of a cone V if it is of the form $K = V \cap H$, where H is a hyperplane in X ($0 \notin H$) and any point of V can be expressed as λx , where $\lambda \geq 0$ and $x \in K$.

Consider a real vector space X ordered by a proper cone V that generates X (i.e. $X = V - V$). We assume that V has base K located on the hyperplane H ($0 \notin H$). Moreover, we assume that K has an additional property: its symmetric convex span

$$B = co(K \cup -K)$$

is radially compact, i.e., $\{\lambda \mid \lambda \rho \in B\}$ is a compact subset of \mathbb{R} for every $\rho \in B, \rho \neq 0$.

Based on these assumptions, we note that the Minkowski functional

$$\|\rho\| = \inf\{\alpha > 0 \mid \rho \in \alpha B\} \tag{2.1}$$

is a norm on X , and that the closed unit ball for this norm is given by the formula

$$\{\rho \in V \mid \|\rho\| \leq 1\} = B$$

(See [1, Proposition II.1.12] for details).

Definition 2.2. (4, 1.10. Definition)] *An ordered normed vector space X with generating cone V is called a base norm space if the norm can be obtained as in (2.1) from the base K of the cone V , such that the set $B = co(K \cup -K)$ is radially compact. In this case, the convex set K is called the distinguished base of V .*

Now we give the necessary information from the theory of facially symmetric spaces.

Let Z be a real or complex normed space. Let us define the orthogonality of elements in this space as follows: the elements $f, g \in Z$ are called *mutually orthogonal*, denoted by $f \diamond g$, if $\|f + g\| = \|f - g\| = \|f\| + \|g\|$. By Z_1 we denote the unit ball of space Z .

A *norm-exposed face* of a unit ball Z_1 of space Z is a non-empty set (not coincident with Z_1) of the form $F_x = \{f \in Z_1: f(x) = 1\}$, where $x \in Z^*, \|x\| = 1$. For any subset $S \subset Z$, we put $S^\circ = \{f \in Z: f \diamond g, \forall g \in S\}$ and call S° the *orthogonal complement* of S . The subsets $S, T \subset Z$ are

called *orthogonal* ($S \diamond T$), if $f \diamond g$ for all $(f, g) \in S \times T$. An element $u \in Z^*$ is called a *projective unit* if $\|u\| = 1$ and $\langle u, F_u^\circ \rangle = 0$. By \mathfrak{F} and \mathfrak{U} we denote the set of norm-exposed faces of Z_1 and projective units in Z_1^* , respectively. $F \in \mathfrak{F}$ is called a *symmetric face* if there exists a linear isometry S_F from Z to Z with $S_F^2 = I$, such that the set of fixed points of S_F is $\overline{sp}F \oplus F^\circ$. We call S_F a *symmetry*.

Definition 2.3. A real or complex normed space Z is called a *weakly facially symmetric space* (WFS-space) if every norm-exposed face of Z_1 is symmetric.

$u \in \mathfrak{U}$ is called a *geometric tripotent* if $F := F_u$ is a symmetric face and $S_F^*u = u$ for some symmetry S_F corresponding to F . By $S\mathfrak{F}$ and $G\mathfrak{U}$ we denote the sets of all symmetric faces of Z_1 and geometric tripotents in Z^* , respectively.

In the WFS-space Z , the *generalized (or geometric) Peirce projections* $P_k(u)$, $k = \{0,1,2\}$ are defined for each symmetric face F_u , as follows:

$$P_1(u) = \frac{1}{2}(I - S_{F_u}), \quad P_1(u)(Z) = \{f \in Z: S_{F_u}f = -f\}$$

$P_0(u)$ and $P_2(u)$ project Z onto F_u° and $\overline{sp}F_u$, respectively.

For convenience, we introduce the following notations:

$$P_k(u)(Z) = Z_k(u), \quad Z_k^*(u) = U_k(u), \quad S_{F_u} = S_u$$

where $k \in \{1,2,3\}$.

A contractive projection Q on a normed space Z is called *neutral* if for any $f \in Z$, $Qf = f$ follows from $\|Qf\| = \|f\|$.

A normed space Z is called *neutral* if for every symmetric face F_u the corresponding projection $P_2(u)$ is neutral.

Definition 2.4. A WFS-space Z is called a *strongly facially symmetric space* (SFS-space) if for every symmetric face F_u of Z_1 and every $v \in Z^*$ with $\|v\| = 1$ and $F_u \subset F_v$ we have $S_u^*v = v$.

Definition 2.5. Let Z be an SFS-space and $u, v \in G\mathfrak{U}$. If $F_u \subset F_v$, then we write $u \leq v$.

3. The connection between the base norm and facially symmetric spaces

In [15], the following properties of the norm-exposed face of the unit ball in a normed space were defined and analyzed.

Definition 3.1 (see [15, Definition 2.1]). A norm-exposed face F of the unit ball of a normed space Z is said to have the property of the Jordan decomposition if

$$(sp_R F)_1 \subset co(IF \cup -IF),$$

where I is a closed unit interval.

Theorem 3.2. Let Z be a real normed space. If the norm-exposed face F_ω of a unit ball Z_1 has the property of a Jordan decomposition and $sp_R F_\omega = Z$, then Z is a base norm space generating by a cone V_ω , the base of which is F_ω and the unit ball Z_1 coincides with the set $B = co(F_\omega \cup -F_\omega)$.

Proof. Let us first show that if F is a face of a unit ball Z_1 of space Z , then the set $B = co(F \cup -F)$ is radially compact and the set $V = \{\alpha f: \forall f \in F, \alpha \in \mathbb{R} \text{ and } \alpha \geq 0\} \subset X$ is a cone. Indeed, let $\alpha\rho \in B$ i.e. $= tf + (1-t)g$, where $f \in F, g \in -F$ and $t \in [0,1]$ for $\rho \in B(\rho \neq 0)$ and $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$. Then $\|\alpha\rho\| \leq 1$, hence $|\alpha| \leq \frac{1}{\|\rho\|}$, so the set $\{\alpha \mid \alpha\rho \in B\}$ is a compact subset of \mathbb{R} , hence B is radially compact.

To show that V is a cone, check that conditions (i) and (ii) of Definition 2.1 are satisfied:

(i) let $x \in V$ and $\lambda \geq 0$, then $x = \alpha f$, where $f \in F$ and $\alpha \geq 0$. Hence, $\lambda x = \lambda \alpha f$. Since $\lambda \alpha \geq 0$, then $\lambda x \in V$;

(ii) let $x, y \in V$, then $x = \alpha f$ and $y = \beta g$, where $f, g \in F$ and $\alpha, \beta \geq 0$. It is clear that if $\alpha \wedge \beta = 0$ then $x + y \in V$. If $\alpha, \beta > 0$ then

$$x + y = \alpha f + \beta g = (\alpha + \beta) \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha + \beta} f + \frac{\beta}{\alpha + \beta} g \right).$$

Since, $\alpha + \beta > 0$ и $\left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha + \beta} f + \frac{\beta}{\alpha + \beta} g \right) \in F$, then we have that $x + y \in V$. Clearly, in this case F is the base of the cone. The theorem is proved. ■

It follows from [15, Lemma 2.3] and [14, Lemma 3.10, Lemma 3.11] that if a norm-exposed face $F = F_\omega$ of a unit ball of a normed space has the Jordan decomposition property, then

$$(sp_R F_\omega)_1 = co(F_\omega \cup -F_\omega)$$

At $sp_R F_\omega = Z$ we obtain the equality $Z_1 = co(F_\omega \cup -F_\omega)$ and for the cone V_ω , the base of which is F , we have $Z = V_\omega - V_\omega$, i.e. Z is the base norm space generated by a cone V_ω .

If the neutral SFS-space is a dual space (see [15, Subsection 2.2]), then every norm-exposed face F of a unit ball Z_1 is weakly *-compact. Then it follows from [15, Lemma 2.6 (b)] and from the Jordan decomposition property that $sp_C F$ is closed, so $Z_2(F) = sp_C F$. If Z is a real neutral SFS-space, then $Z_2(F_u) = sp_R F$.

Definition 3.3. Let Z be a SFS-space. A geometric tripotent $\omega \in G\mathcal{U}$ is called unitary if $Z_1 = co(F_\omega \cup -F_\omega)$.

Clearly, if ω is a unitary geometric tripotent on a real SFS-space Z , then $sp F_\omega = Z$. Because of this and of Theorem 3.2, the following corollaries follow.

Corollary 3.4. Let Z be a real SFS-space. A geometric tripotent $\omega \in G\mathcal{U}$ is unitary if and only if F_ω has the Jordan decomposition property and $sp F_\omega = Z$.

For an example, consider the space \mathbb{R}^n , whose unit ball is a cocube:

$$B = \left\{ (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) : \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i| \leq 1 \right\}$$

It follows from [18, Theorem 4.1] that in this case the space \mathbb{R}^n is an SFS-space, the symmetric face $F_u \in B$ with vertices $\{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n\}$, where $f_i = (0, 0, \dots, x_i, \dots, 0)$ and $x_i = 1$, has the Jordan decomposition property and $sp F_u = \mathbb{R}^n$, and the geometric tripotent $u = (1, 1, \dots, 1)$ is unitary.

The following statement, which follows from Theorem 3.2 and Corollary 3.4 establishes the generality between the base norm and SFS spaces and therefore reveals a new approach to study the theory of facially symmetric spaces.

Corollary 3.5. Let Z be a real SFS-space and ω be a fixed unitary geometric tripotent. Then Z is a base norm space generating by a cone V_ω , the base of which is F_ω and $Z_1 = co(F_\omega \cup -F_\omega)$.

There exist SFS-spaces in the unit ball of the dual space of which, there is no unitary geometric tripotent. For instance, let's consider the space $Z = \mathbb{R}^n$ with norm

$$\|x\| = \sqrt{x_1^2 + x_2^2} + |x_3| + \dots + |x_n|$$

In [19, Theorem 2] it is shown that in this case Z is a neutral SFS-space of rank $n - 1$. Moreover, for any symmetric face F_u of a unit ball Z_1 we have $sp F_u \neq Z$, therefore, the geometric

tripotent u is not unitary. Since the mapping $G\mathcal{U}\ni u \mapsto F_u \in S\mathfrak{F}$ is a bijection in SFS -space (see [9, Proposition 1.4]), there is no unitary geometric tripotent in the given unit ball Z_1^* .

However, there are classes of SFS -spaces in whose unit ball there always exist symmetric faces such that their linear span coincides with the given space. For example, in [10, Proposition 4.1] it is proved that in a neutral SFS -space Z for any $u \in G\mathcal{U}$, the subspaces $Z_k(u) (k \in \{0,1,2\})$ are SFS -spaces, therefore $spF_u = Z_2(u)$ is an SFS -space. In this case, we get the following statement.

Corollary 3.6. *Let Z be a real neutral SFS -space and a symmetric face F_u have the property of Jordan decomposition in SFS -space $Z_2(u)$. Then $Z_2(u)$ is a base norm space generating by a cone V_u , the base of which is F_u and $(spF_u)_1 = co(F_u \cup -F_u)$.*

REFERENCES

1. Alfsen E.M., Compact convex sets and boundary integrals, *Ergebnisse Math.* 57, Springer-Verlag, New York, Heidelberg, 1971.
2. Alfsen E., Shultz F., State spaces of Jordan algebras, *Acta Math.*, 140 (1978), 155-190.
3. Alfsen E., Hanche-Olsen H, Shultz F., State spaces of C^* -algebras, *Acta Math.*, 144(1980), 267-305.
4. Alfsen E., Shultz F., State Spaces of Operator Algebras, Basic Theory, Orientation and C^* -products, Birkhäuser, Boston, 2001.
5. Dang T., Real isometries between JB^* -triples, *Proceedings of the American mathematical society* volume 114, number 4, April 1992.
6. Edwards C.M., Hügli R.V., Rüttimann G.T., A geometric characterization of structural projections on a JBW^* -triple, *J. Funct. Anal.* 202 (2003), no. 1,174 – 194.
7. Friedman Y., Russo B., Structure of the predual of a JBW^* -triple, *J. Reine Angew. Math.* 356 (1985), 67-89.
8. Friedman Y., Russo B., A Gelfand-Naimark Theorem for JB^* -triples, *Duke Math. J.* 53 (1986), 139-148.
9. Friedman Y., Russo B., A geometric spectral theorem, *Quart. J. Math. Oxford.* 1986. Vol. 37. 2. p. 263-277.
10. Friedman Y., Russo B., Affine structure of facially symmetric spaces, *Math. Proc. Cambridge Philos. Soc.* 106 (1989) 107-124.
11. Friedman Y., Russo B., Some affine geometric aspects of operator algebras, *Pac. J. Math.* 137(1989), 123-144.
12. Friedman Y., Russo B., Geometry of the Dual ball of the Spin Factor, *Proc. Lon. Math. Soc.* 65 (1992), p. 142-174.
13. Friedman Y., Russo B., Classification of atomic facially symmetric spaces, *Canad. J. Math.* - 1993. - № 1 (45). - P. 33-87.
14. Ibragimov M.M., Geometric properties of neutral facially symmetric spaces. *Uzbek Mathematical Journal* 2023, Volume 67, Issue 2, pp.60-66.
15. Neal M., Russo B., State space of JB^* -triples, *Math. Ann.* - 2004. -V. 328.N 4. - P. 585-624.
16. Upmeyer H., *Jordan Algebras in Analysis, Operator Theory, and Quantum Mechanics*, CBMS Regional Conf. Ser. in Math. no. 67 (Conference Board Math. Sci., 1987).
17. Аюпов Ш. А., Ядгоров Н.Ж., Спектральные выпуклые множества в конечномерных пространствах, *Известия АН УзССР, сер. физ.-мат. наук.* 1989. № 3, стр. 3-7